

The Ohio State University

Department of Anthropology

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April 29, 1981

Mr. Peter Morgan
The Ashmolean Museum
Department of Eastern Art
Oxford OX1 2PH
England

Dear Mr. Morgan:

J. W. Allan recently answered my query, originally addressed to Dr. Moorey concerning the Marv Dasht (sometimes called Kur River Basin) survey material that Andrew Williamson was studying. It is my understanding that the letter was then turned over to you for reply.

In re-reading Dr. Allan's letter it occurred to me that there might be some slight mis-understanding. The Marv Dasht/Kur River Basin material constitutes only a very small proportion of Andrew's survey collection. He surveyed almost all of Fars and the vast bulk of his material comes from other parts of the province. I understand that you are working on the publication of the Sirjan material but it is unclear to me whether or not you also wish to publish the wider range of the Fars survey material.

Let me assure you that I have no desire to raise any question over rights to any if this material. I am directly interested only in the Marv Dasht collection and that only if no one else intends to work on it.

In my opinion Andrew's Fars survey and his work at Sirjan should constitute an important contribution to Islamic archaeological studies.

I hope you are successful in the endeavor and if you do not intend to deal with the Marv Dasht material I would appreciate very much your assistance in making any information on the collection available to Dr. Donald Whitcomb.

Sincerely yours,

William M. Sumner
Associate Professor

WMS:KAM